

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADVERTISING (MARKETING) IN INCREASING BUSINESS EFFICIENCY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the importance of advertising and marketing in increasing the efficiency of an enterprise. Marketing strategies are studied, the role of advertising in satisfying consumer needs, forming a brand image and increasing competitiveness. It also considers the effectiveness of modern marketing tools, including digital marketing, promotion through social networks and advertising strategies aimed at customers. The results of the study are aimed at providing recommendations to enterprises on improving marketing strategies and conducting effective advertising campaigns.

Keywords: Marketing business, marketing term, enterprises, your business, business development, marketing to customers.

Introduction.

The concept of marketing is not new to people today. If we come to the scientific meaning of this concept, which is of great importance for the 21st century, marketing (English: market - market, movement in the market, activity) is a form of organization and management of the production and sale of goods by an enterprise. Unlike other functions of business activity, marketing mainly deals with issues related to consumers. There are many opinions about when marketing appeared. If we associate the origin of marketing with advertising, then in Babylon, in 3000 BC, a reward was first announced and publicly proclaimed for the capture of a runaway slave. One of the most persistent points of view is that the first elements of marketing (verbal advertising, agreement on forms of exchange) appeared from the moment when humanity got rid of the isolation of the natural economy and forms of trade appeared. However, if we recognize that advertising is an important function of marketing, then it is worth recalling that three thousand years ago in Babylon there were special signs promising a reward for runaway slaves: two oxen. It is customary to consider the first major stage of marketing evolution from the beginning of the 20th century to the mid-1930s¹.

Marketing and its Importance for Businesses

In this section, we will discuss the importance of marketing for businesses along with the reasons.

- **Effective Customer Engagement:** Businesses need to engage customers and this is where marketing proves to be an effective tool. Customers can be

engaged by telling them what they don't know and by creating good content around your products and services.

- **Building and Maintaining Reputation:** The reputation of your business is what determines how it grows and how long it lasts. This is where marketing comes in as a way to build the brand equity of the business. And this happens when the expectations of the customers are met.

- **Building Relationships between Customers and the Business:** For any business to thrive, it needs to build long-term relationships with its customers. Marketing is based on demographics, psychographics and consumer behavior and therefore allows you to understand what the customers want.

- **Increasing Sales:** Since marketing uses different methods to promote products or services, it helps in increasing the chances of making good sales. Happy customers automatically become brand ambassadors for the company.

- **Relevance:** Marketing helps the business to remain relevant to its customers and its industry. This helps in maintaining good relationships.

- **Informed decision making:** The main questions that concern every business are how and why to produce a product or provide services. This highlights the importance of marketing to the business and how it connects the business and the society.

Types of Marketing:

B2B Marketing: The term B2B marketing refers to business-to-business transactions. B2B marketing strategies are used when a company sells products or services to another company.

B2C Marketing: B2C marketing refers to business-to-consumer marketing. This refers to a company selling its products or services to consumers and the promotion of the business is done through advertising.

C2B Marketing: This is the opposite of B2C and refers to marketing from consumer to business. In this type of marketing, the consumer provides goods or services to the company.

C2C marketing: C2C marketing refers to consumer-to-consumer marketing. In this case, consumers interact with co-authors when they share a common product or service. Examples of this are OfferUp and permission applications.

Literature review: Scientists have defined marketing differently. Russian scientist I.K. Belyaevsky said: "Marketing is a system of studying, organizing, and managing the market." The famous European marketer Jean-Jacques Lambin defines marketing as follows: "Marketing is a social process aimed at satisfying the wants and needs of organizations and individuals through the free competitive exchange of goods and services," "Marketing is both a business philosophy and an active process." According to Igor Mann, "the main task of marketing is to acquire and retain customers. Period." Charles De Gaulle put forward the idea that "Always choose the most difficult path - then you will not meet competitors." Zinov Davidov expressed the idea that "I have never been involved in marketing. I only loved my customers." According to A. Soliev, the

marketing philosophy requires that entrepreneurial activity or business line - action should be focused only on the consumer².

Kotler, Ph. (Author of Marketing) – Kotler defines marketing as a customer-oriented management system. He does not associate marketing with sales or advertising alone, but rather as an integral part of the overall business strategy. In his opinion, marketing is necessary to correctly understand the needs of customers and develop services or products accordingly in order to increase the efficiency of the enterprise. Distinguishing oneself from competitors and offering high value to customers is one of the main tasks of marketing.

Michael Porter (Strategic Management Expert) – According to Porter's theory of "competitive advantages", marketing is an important element in creating a competitive advantage for an enterprise. He emphasizes the use of marketing in developing effective strategies, correctly analyzing the market and choosing competitive strategies based on the company's resources. The role of marketing is to offer a product or service based on customer needs and create a high level of value.

Philip Kotler and Gary Armstrong (Founders of Marketing Management) – They emphasize that the main task of marketing is to satisfy customer needs. In their opinion, marketing includes not only increasing sales, but also strengthening the brand, establishing long-term relationships with customers and increasing customer loyalty. At the same time, marketing effectively allocates resources, helps the company develop and increases overall efficiency.

David A. Aaker (Brand Management Expert) – Aaker focuses on the importance of marketing on strengthening the brand and achieving long-term success. Brand development is carried out through marketing, since brand strength plays an important role in attracting customers and conquering the market. Effective marketing creates a brand and through it helps the enterprise strengthen its position in its market.

Sh. T. Uktamov (Marketing Expert) – Uzbek scientist Sh. T. Uktamov does not see marketing only as a sales activity, but he defines it as an important tool for managing the overall activities of the enterprise and developing a successful strategy. He calls marketing "customer-oriented management" and emphasizes the need to effectively apply marketing in all areas, including production, sales, and services, to increase the overall efficiency of the enterprise.

A. R. Akramov (Economist and marketing specialist) – Akramov shows the important role of marketing in increasing competitiveness. He emphasizes that through marketing, enterprises can create their own competitive advantages by conducting in-depth market analysis and correctly understanding customer needs. Akramov also emphasizes the need for effective marketing management based on the marketing mix (4P: product, price, place, advertising) system.

M. A. Usmanov (Marketing Specialist) – Usmanov in his works shows marketing as a strengthening factor in the development of an enterprise. He

evaluates marketing as a necessary tool for enterprises to correctly segment the market, establish effective relationships with customers by offering them suitable products and services. He emphasizes that ensuring customer loyalty and improving the quality of services are one of the main tasks of marketing.

B. A. Mavlonov (Marketing Research) – Mavlonov calls marketing “the art of understanding the market and customers”. He considers marketing to be an important factor in implementing an innovative approach for enterprises. With the help of marketing, companies can overcome competition in the introduction of new technologies, products and services and achieve full satisfaction of customer needs. He also considers marketing to be important as a means of establishing constant communication between the company and customers and developing a brand.

Conclusion.

The importance of advertising and marketing strategies in increasing the efficiency of the enterprise is incomparable. In modern market conditions, effective marketing approaches allow you to correctly identify customer needs, form a brand image and increase sales. The results of the study show that tools such as digital marketing, contextual advertising, and promotion through social networks can significantly increase the company's profits.

Also, proper planning of marketing strategies plays an important role in ensuring the competitiveness of the enterprise in the market. Through innovative advertising technologies and in-depth analysis of consumer behavior, companies can effectively promote their products and increase consumer loyalty.

This article covers the basic principles of marketing strategies, the impact of advertising on efficiency, and the advantages of using advertising technologies in various industries. With the development of digital technologies in the future, it is expected that the marketing and advertising industry will require even more innovative approaches. Therefore, businesses need to adapt to market conditions and actively use new marketing tools.

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